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The Epidemiological Pattern of Psychosis in Military Patients

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Abstract

Background: The schizophrenic breakdown rate of recruits to the US army was much higher in their first month of military service taken at any time in the next two years suggesting that the transition from civilian life to recruiting barracks was contributing to the genesis of these illnesses.

Objectives: The aim of this study is to explore, retrospectively, the epidemiological pattern of psychosis in military patients including family history, scholastic achievement, social status and precipitating factors.

Patients and methods: The case records of 100 psychotic patients were reviewed. Most of the cases were clinically diagnosed in Al Rasheed military hospital during 2001 - 2002 as having schizophrenic. The case records included clinical notes of the general practitioner and specialist in addition to family, social and military records.

Results: Out of the 100 cases, 32 were volunteer conscripts and 68 were compulsory recruits. Seventy six patients

illness. The majority of psychotic patients were with low scholastic achievement, attributed mostly to early onset of the illness and social stigma. The precipitating factor of the impact of the demanding new military life is more evident than family history so the most important preventive measure to address is to improve handling of transference of societies from civilian life to military one.

Conclusion: Military discipline could be considered as stressful factor that precipitates the illness.

Key Words: Psychosis-Military patients-Pattern

Introduction

The variable course of psychotic disorders has been well documented in the literature. However, the understanding of different combinations of biological predisposition, clinical characteristics and psychosocial environment accounting for different illnesses remains illusive. It has been asserted that each dimension of psychotic outcome is best predicted by what has happened earlier [1]. The term "psychotic" denotes loss of reality testing which can occur as a result of delusional belief or hallucinatory perception, usually auditory or visual. The psychotic symptoms are the most

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were single, 30 had a positive family history of psychiatric illness and 54 had a stressful factor prior to the onset of the

dramatic and potentially dangerous features of this illness, but other symptoms may be even more disabling [2]. Genetic factors are likely to be important in schizophrenia, but it can also be familial, because family members share the same disadvantaged environment [3]. Paul Meehl [4] in his integrative model that led to the development of the diathesis-stress model suggested that certain people possess a genetic predisposition to schizophrenia and other psychotic disorders, which are expressed behaviorally only if they are reared in a stressful environment. On other hand, if environmental stress remains below the person's stress threshold, schizophrenia may never develop even in persons at genetic risk.

A role has been suggested for adverse life events and social adversity as operating factors on already predisposed individuals to trigger onset [5]. Schizophrenic patients experience a significantly higher frequency of such events during the 3-week period prior to the onset of their symptoms [6]. The schizophrenic breakdown rate of recruits to the US army was much higher in their first month of military service taken at any time in the next two years suggesting that the transition from civilian life to recruiting barracks was contributing to the genesis of these illnesses [7]. It was reported that such pre-schizophrenic children showed lower I.Q. and poor scholastic performance [8]. It was suggested that life events serve to trigger the florid onset in those who are predisposed [9].

Patients and methods

The case records of 100 psychotic patients were reviewed. Most of the cases were clinically diagnosed in Al Rasheed military hospital during 2001 - 2002 as having schizophrenic. The case records included clinical notes of the general practitioner and specialist in addition to family, social and military records.

Results

Out of the 100 cases, 32 were volunteer conscripts and 68 were compulsory recruits. Single men constituted 76 cases while the remaining 24 were married men. Figure (1) shows that 37 patients completed elementary school only, 38 completed intermediate school, 13 completed secondary school and 12 completed colleges.

Figure (1): Scholastic Achievement of the Studied Cases

A positive family history of the illness was found in 30 patients, 13 of them had also a stressful factor prior to the onset of their illness, 21 patients were reared without their fathers and 9 patients were reared without their mothers.

Just over one half of the cases (51) were admitted to the hospital more than 3 times, 35 patients had 3 admissions, and 14 patients had 2 previous admissions. A course of Electroconvulsive Therapy (ECT) was used for the treatment of 61 patients during their admission. Precipitating factors: 54 patients had a variety of stressors which are considered as precipitating factors preceding the onset of the illness. In addition to these factors, 13 patients also had a positive family history of the illness. These factors occurred during the first 3 weeks prior to the onset of the illness in 39 patients while in 15 patients they preceded the onset of the illness by at least 6 months.

Discussion

The majority of patients (68%) were recruited soldiers, which may indicate that military discipline could be considered as stressful factor that precipitates the illness according to Steinberg and Durnel study [7]. Low level of Scholastic achievement in the sample may be related to the early onset of the disease process which goes with the results of the study of Jones et al [8]. The majority of patients (76%) were single which may be related to the result of the disease process itself and the social stigma and label, which may be considered as an obstacle to marriage. A positive family history of psychiatric illness was found in 30 cases, 13 of whom also had a stressful factor prior to the onset of the illness which is consistent with the results of many other studies [3, 4, 5, 9]. Stressful events / factors were reported by 54 patients to have happened prior to the onset of illness. This event was the

only factor that determines or expresses the disease process in 41 patients, especially in the first three weeks prior to the onset of the illness which agrees with the results of many studies [4, 6, 7].

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